

Direct and derivative spectrophotometric determination of iron(III) with 2,4-dihydroxy benzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone in plant and pharmaceutical samples

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A simple, sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of iron(III) in aqueous solution. The metal ion forms yellowish-brown coloured, soluble complex with 2,4-dihydroxy benzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone (2,4-DHBINH) at pH 3.0 with λ_{\max} at 400 nm. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.07–2.20 $\mu\text{g/ml}^{-1}$ of Fe^{III} . The molar absorptivity and the Sandell's sensitivity of the method are $1.75 \pm 0.025 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0034 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ at 400 nm respectively. The interference of various ions has been studied. The complex has a 1 : 1 [Fe^{III} : 2,4-DHBINH] stoichiometry. A method for the determination of Fe^{III} by first order derivative spectrophotometry has also been proposed.

Most of the spectrophotometric methods for determination of iron involve iron(II)¹ and only one on iron(III)² complexes. Spectrophotometric methods for determination of Fe^{III} using isonicotinoyl hydrazones are rare. The present paper reports the spectrophotometric determination of Fe^{III} in plant, human blood samples and pharmaceutical samples.

Experimental

2,4-DHBINH was prepared by condensing 2,4-dihydroxy benzaldehyde and isonicotinic acid hydrazide in methanol³ (m.p. 290°C). A 0.01 M solution in dimethylformamide (DMF) was used in the studies. Stock solution of Fe^{III} was prepared by dissolving requisite quantity of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (A.R., B.D.H.) in 100 ml of doubly distilled water (0.01 M) and standardized⁴. Buffer solutions were prepared by employing 1 M HCl and 1 M sodium acetate (pH 1 to 3), and 0.2 M sodium acetate and 0.2 M acetic acid (pH 3.5 to 6.0) and was checked by using pH meter. Shimadzu UV visible spectrophotometer (Model UV-160 A) and Philips digital pH meter (Model PP 9046) were employed for absorbance and pH measurements respectively.

Procedure :

Direct spectrophotometry :

In a set of 10 ml flasks, 5 ml buffer solution (pH 3.0), 3 ml of DMF, varying amounts of Fe^{III} solution, 0.2 ml of 0.5 M thiourea [to mask Cu^{II}] and 0.2 ml of the reagent (1×10^{-2} M) in DMF were added and made up to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance was measured at 400 nm against the reagent blank. The calibration curve was prepared by plotting the absorbance against the amount of Fe^{III} .

First derivative spectrophotometry :

For the above solutions, first order derivative spectra were recorded with a scan speed of fast (nearly 2400 nm min^{-1}), slit width of 1 nm, with degrees of freedom 9, in the wavelength range from 350–600 nm. The derivative peak height was measured by peak-zero method at 400 nm. The peak height was plotted against the amount of Fe^{III} to obtain the calibration curve.

Linear calibration graphs were obtained and calibration equations were calculated as $y(A) = 0.298C + 0.0002$ for zero order data and $y(A) = 0.146C - 0.0002$ for the derivative data by fitting experimental data.

Results and discussion

The absorption spectra of the reagent and the complex were recorded in the wavelength range 350–550 nm at pH 3.0 against the buffer solution and reagent blank, respectively. The complex shows an absorption maximum at 400 nm. The reagent has negligible absorbance at this wavelength.

The spectrophotometric determination was carried out at pH 3.0, at which the intensity of the developed colour is maximum. A two fold molar excess of 2,4-DHBINH was necessary for complete colour development.

Applicability of Beer's law :

From the calibration plot, it is observed that in the present method Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 0.07–2.20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Fe^{III} . The molar absorptivity of the complex at 400 nm and at pH 3.0 is $1.75 \pm 0.025 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The Sandell's sensitivity is $0.0034 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

Other statistical data derived for the present method are as follows. The standard deviation of the method for ten determinations of 1.18 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Fe^{III} is found to be 0.005. The slope, intercept and correlation coefficient (γ) of the equation for experimental data are 0.298, 0.0002 and 0.990 respectively.

The composition of the complex was determined by the Job's and mole ratio methods and found to be 1 : 1 [Fe^{III} : 2,4-DHBINH]. The stability constant of β of the complex calculated from the Job's method is 9.26×10^6 . The spectral curve of the iron(III) complex has its peak at 420 nm and Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.1 to 3.6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Fe^{III} .

The effect of various diverse ions on the determination of Fe^{III} was studied to find out the tolerance levels of these diverse ions in the present method. The tolerance limit of a foreign ion was taken as the amount that caused an error in the absorbance value by $\pm 2\%$. The data are presented in Table 1. The large amounts of commonly associated cations and anions do not interfere in the determination of Fe^{III} .

Table 1. Tolerance limit of diverse ions in the determination of Fe^{III}

Ion	Amount of $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}} = 1.18 \mu\text{g/ml}$	
	Tolerance limit ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Tolerance limit ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
Iodate	1500	Ca^{II} 500
Thiourea	1500	Na^{I} 400
Thiocyanate	1100	K^{I} 400
Chloride	500	Cr^{III} 200
Sulphate	500	Cd^{II} 200
Nitrate	500	Ce^{IV} 200
Nitrite	500	Mn^{II} 200
Tartrate	200	Ba^{II} 200
Fluoride	190	Mg^{II} 200
		Zn^{II} 200
		Pb^{II} 50, 100 ^a
		Co^{II} 60
		Cu^{II} 60 ^a
		Ni^{II} 30
		Zr^{IV} 30 ^b
		Al^{III} 30 ^b
		Mo^{VI} 20
		Tl^{IV} 20 ^b

^aMasked with 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of thiourea. ^bMasked with 150 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of fluoride.

Other statistical data derived for the present method are as follows. The standard deviations of the method for ten determinations of 1.18 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Fe^{III} is 0.004. The correla-

tion coefficient (γ) of the calibration equation is of the experimental data is 0.9999.

The spectrophotometric method developed is applied for the determination of Fe^{III} in plant, human blood samples and iron capsules (multivitamin and multimineral capsules). The grape leaf and the banana samples are supplied by Andhra Pradesh Agricultural Research Institute (APARI), Hyderabad, India. The blood sample is collected from Nizam Institute of Medical Sciences (NIMS), Hyderabad, India. The blood sample solution is prepared by the procedure described in the literature⁵. 10 ml of blood sample is taken in a Kjeidahl flask and heated with 10 ml of the mixture of nitric, sulphuric and perchloric acids (taken in the ratio 3 : 1 : 1). The mixture is evaporated to dryness. The residue is dissolved in 5 ml of slightly acidified water by heating. The solution is transferred quantitatively into a 100 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark with distilled water. The solution is further diluted as required. In order to determine iron(III) content of multivitamin and multimineral capsules, the capsules are brought into solution by adapting the following procedure : Accurately weighed 0.1 g of the capsule is thoroughly powdered and taken in a platinum crucible and ashed by igniting in a muffle furnace at a controlled temperature of 500°C. The ash is dissolved by heating with 10 ml of 1 : 1 HCl, filtered through an acid washed filter paper into a 100 ml volumetric flask and the residue is washed with hot water. The washings are also collected into the volumetric flasks and finally made up to the mark with distilled water. The solution is further diluted as required.

Table 2. Analysis of iron(III)

Sample	Amount of iron(III) ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)					
	Zero order			First derivative		
	APARI	Present	Error	APARI	Present	Error
for (i) method* and (ii) and AAS for (iii) and (iv) values			(%)	values	method*	(%)
(i) Leaf sample grape	55.40	55.60	0.4	55.49	55.80	0.7
(ii) Banana fruit	16.00	15.80	-1.3	16.00	15.90	-0.6
(iii) Multivitamin multimineral capsule (Glaxo)	41.40	40.90	-0.5	41.10	41.20	-0.2
(iv) Human blood	771.80**	768.20**	-0.5	771.80**	760.00**	-1.5

*Average of six determinations. ** $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

General procedure :

A known aliquot of sample is taken in a 10 ml volumetric flask containing 5 ml buffer of pH 3.0, 3 ml DMF, 0.2 ml 0.5 M thiourea [to mask Cu^{II}] and 0.2 ml reagent (1×10^{-2} M) solution and made up to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance was measured at 400 nm for zero order and at 420 nm for the first order derivative mode. The absorbance values are referred to the pre-determined calibration plot to compute the amount of Fe^{III}. The results showed in Tables 2 are in good agreement with certified or standard values.

References

1. G. L. Traister and A. A. Schilt, *Anal. Chem.*, 1976, **48**, 216; T. Korenaga, S. Motomizu and T. Koremaga, *Anal. Chem. Acta*, 1973, **65**, 335; K. Toei, S. Motomizo and T. Koremaga, *Analyst*, 1976, **101**, 974; Y. Nakamura, H. Nagai, D. Kubota and S. Himeno, *Benseki Kagaku*, 1973, **22**, 1156; Y. Shizo, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1975, **48**, 2798; S. O. Kobayakova, V. M. Savostina and V. M. Pestikova, *Zh. Analik. Khim.*, 1974, **29**, 300; S.O. Kolyakova, V. M. Savostina, S. A. Lomonosar and M. V. Lomonosor, *Zh. Analik. Khim.*, 1971, **26**, 1277.
2. M. Roman Ceba, J. A. Arreboa Rmira and J. J. Berzas Navado, *Talanta*, 1982, **29**, 142.
3. P. T. Sah and S. A. Peoples, *J. Am. Pharm. Assoc. Sci. Ed.*, 1954, **43**, 513.
4. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., ELBS and Longman, 1975, 325.
5. M. L. Cluet and J. H. Yoe, *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, **29**, 1265.